

A new heterogeneous precipitate based ion selective electrode for cesium(I) ion

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A new ion selective electrode for measurement of Cs⁺ ion has been developed using cesium tetraphenyl borate precipitate as electro-active material. The characteristics of the electrode has been studied. The electrode was found to be selective in presence of Ca^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ba^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ag^I, Na^I and K^I. The application of the electrode for volumetric determination of cesium in solution has been demonstrated.

Among the first group elements, the selective and sensitive to hydrogen, lithium, sodium and potassium ions are well known. New electrodes for these four ions continue to appear in the literature¹. Ion selective electrodes for sodium and potassium ions are also commercially available². However, comparatively very less work has been done towards the development of cesium(I) ion selective electrode. Interest in determination of Cs⁺ ion by different techniques continues to grow because of occurrence of cesium ions in environmental samples³. The earliest cesium membrane electrode prepared was in the form of a pellet made from cesium 12-molybdophosphate. This was mixed with G.E. silicone, partly dried and pressed at 1600 psi into a circular disc like pellet about 3 mm thick⁴. This electrode has been used in precipitation reactions involving cesium(I) and molybdophosphoric acid. A number of electrodes for Cs⁺ ion have been reported⁵. Johansson and Lars⁶ prepared a Cs⁺ selective electrode from crystalline synthetic zeolite. The development of new cesium ion selective electrode continues to draw attention of scientists all over the world⁷. Recently Agai *et al.*⁸ have developed an electrode based on bis(benzo 18-crown-6) ionophores.

We have developed a new solid state heterogeneous membrane electrode for Cs⁺ using cesium tetraphenylborate as electroactive material in epoxy resin as matrix.

Results and discussion

Electrode response : Various concentrations of Cs⁺ ion solution were prepared and their potentials noted using the cesium electrode and an SCE as reference electrode. The electrode gave a lower detection limit of 5×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ (Fig. 1). Thus it could detect cesium down to this concentration. The slope of the linear portion (1×10^{-1} – 5×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³) of the graph was found to be 55 mV per

Fig. 1. Response curve for cesium(I) electrode and selectivity coefficients.

decade change of cesium ion concentration.

The time taken by the cesium ISE to attain a constant value of potential for a particular concentration was 15 s.

The response of the cesium electrode towards the ion concentration at various pH values shows that in the pH range 4–8 the potential is constant and therefore this is the working pH range of the electrode.

The selectivity coefficients for various divalent and monovalent cations towards the cesium ISE were determined by the mixed solution method⁹. The electrode was found to be selective in presence of Ca^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ba^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ag^I, Li^I, Na^I and K^I (Table 1).

Applications : In order to explore the utility of the electrode it was used as an indicator electrode in the precipita-

Table 1. The concentration of primary ion Cs^+ was varied in the range $1 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ to $1 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and the concentration of the secondary ion was kept constant at $10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Ions	Selectivity coefficients	
	K^{pot}	
Ca^{II}	0.01	
Cu^{II}	0.01	
Ba^{II}	0.03	
Mg^{II}	0.03	
Ag^I	0.50	
Li^I	0.50	
Na^I	0.10	
K^I	0.10	

tion titration of cesium nitrate with sodium tetraphenyl borate. The titration curve (Fig. 2) gives the inflexion point which corresponds to the theoretical equivalent point. Thus volumetric determination of cesium ion in solution is possible using the electrode prepared.

Fig. 2. Precipitation titration of cesium nitrate with sodium tetraphenylborate.

Experimental

Materials and method :

A solution of cesium chloride (B.D.H.) was mixed with sodium tetraphenyl borate (Fluka) to obtain the precipitate of cesium tetraphenyl borate. After drying the precipitate, 0.1 g of it was mixed with 0.4 g of epoxy resin (Araldite-Ciba Giegy) to obtain a paste. This was spread over a filter paper to obtain approximately a 0.1 mm thick layer of the

electroactive material with matrix and left in air to dry for 48 h. It was then dipped in 0.01 mol dm^{-3} solution of the ion concentration for about 24 h and the membrane was separated by peeling off the filter paper.

A disc of the membrane (1 cm) was cut out from the master membrane and attached to one end of the glass tube of bore 0.5 cm with epoxy resin as adhesive. The internal reference solution consisted of 0.01 mol dm^{-3} solution of cesium(I) and saturated calomel electrode for electrical contact. A second SCE was used as external reference electrode. The complete electrode assembly can be diagrammatically represented as : where M is the concentration solution of the ion concerned (0.01 mol dm^{-3}) and * the charge of the ion.

The electrode thus prepared was conditioned by immersing it for 6–7 days in 0.01 mol dm^{-3} solution of the ion for the equilibration of the electrode. The electrode was again dipped for an hour in 0.01 mol dm^{-3} solution of cesium(I) before use in potentiometric measurements.

It was observed that once a electrode is fabricated from the master membrane it functions well for 2–3 months and after which the used membrane must be replaced by new membrane cut from the master membrane.

Instruments :

A Philips pH meter (Model PR 9405M) with a saturated calomel electrode (Elico) as reference electrode was used for making potentiometric measurements. A wrist motion shaker which was electrically operated was used for shaking various solutions. A magnetic stirrer was used for stirring solutions.

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